

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

Departmental Library

Report

2015-16

1. Title of the Practice- "Development Of Departmental Library By The Students Donating Books"

Goals-

1. Encourage students to develop an appreciation for reading and lifelong learning.
2. Provides a learning environment that encourages intellectual exploration and active learning.
3. Serve as college information center for students and teachers.
4. Access and adjust programs to support initiatives and best practices.
5. To motivate the students in feeling of donation

3. The Context-

The departmental library contains

1. Text books
2. Reference books
3. Research magazines
4. Journals
5. Thesis
6. Question paper sets
7. CD's
8. Practice manuals

4. The Practice-

1. Books are issued to needy students
2. In charge of departmental library is Asstt. Prof. S. J. Uke and Laboratory attendant of Physics maintained and issuing register.
3. Books are issued in a circular manner to individual student as well as in group
4. Book is issued only for 7 days

5. Evidence of success-

1. The departmental library helps in expanding the information to meet the needs of students and in turn the society.
2. It maintains supportive and flexible learning environment to accommodate student individual backgrounds needs and aspirations.
3. Increase individuals' strength towards research.
4. Number of students donating books

From session 2015-16 B.Sc. final year students donate books to departmental library after exam

6. Information of textbooks, journal, study material, and reference books in departmental library till June, 2015:

No. of textbooks in departmental library	No. of journal in departmental library	Study material in departmental library	Reference books in departmental library
05	02	04	---

No. of students donating books- 05

List of donated books-

7. Problems encountered and resources required

1. Lack of accommodation and furniture
2. Lack of Wi-Fi
3. Lack of audio visual aids.

H. O. D.

(J. D. Patil)

J. D. Patil Sangli Ikar, Mv. Daryapur

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS

Departmental Library

Report

2014-15

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No. of textbooks in departmental library	No. of journal in departmental library	Study material in departmental library	Reference books in departmental library
04	02	06	---

No. of students donating books- 04

List of donated books-

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2. Lack of Wi-Fi
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H.O.D.

(Dr. D. R. Bambole)

J. D. Patil Sanglu Ikar, Mv. Daryapur

Shri Shvaji Education Society Amravati's
J. D. PATIL SANGLUDKAR MAHAVIDYALAYA, DARYAPUR
DIST- AMRAVATI.

DEPARTMENT OF HISTORY

DEPARTMENTAL LIBRARY

Session:- 2015-16

No. of Textbooks in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	Nature of Study Material in Departmental Library	Nature of Reference Books in Departmental Library
03	02	13	01

Head

Dr. K. G. Sontakke

Shri Shvaji Education Society Amravati's
J. D. PATIL SANGLUDKAR MAHAVIDYALAYA, DARYAPUR
DIST- AMRAVATI.
DEPARTMENT OF HISTORY
DEPARTMENTAL LIBRARY

Session:- 2014-15

No. of Textbooks in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	Nature of Study Material in Departmental Library	Nature of Reference Books in Departmental Library
-	02	04	01

Head

Dr. K. G. Sontakke

J. D. Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur

Department Of Commerce

Departmental Library

Session - 2015-16

No. of Text Book in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	No. of Study Material in Departmental Library	No. of Reference Book in Departmental Library
09	08		

SIGNATURE
Associate Professor & Head
Faculty of Commerce
(H O D)
2015-16, Daryapur

DATE: 27/07/2016
PLACE - Daryapur.

J. D. Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur

Department Of Commerce

Departmental Library

Session – 2015-16

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09	08	-----	-----

SIGNATURE

Associate Professor & Head

Faculty of Commerce

(H. O. D.)

J.D.P.S. Mv., Daryapur

DATE: 27/07/2016

PLACE: - Daryapur.

J. D. Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur

Department Of Commerce

Departmental Library

Session – 2014-15

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06	06	-----	-----

SIGNATURE
Associate Professor & Head
Faculty of Commerce
(H. O. D.)
J.D.P.S. Mv., Daryapur

DATE: 27/07/2016
PLACE:- Daryapur

Jai Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur.

Department of Chemistry

Annual report 2015-16

Staff Members:-

1. Prof U.N.Rathod Head,
2. Prof.S.S.Kadu On FIP leave
3. Prof.R.G.Sawarkar FIP Substitute Teacher
4. & 10 CHB teachers

Department of Chemistry organizes the guest lecturers to Motivate the Students.

1. Dr.Anand S.Burange Ph.D. NCL-Pune, delivered the talk on Scope in Chemistry for undergraduate students the elaborated talk on opportunities in Chemistry after Post Graduation on dated 15 September 2015.
2. Mr.P.G.Vilhekar, PO officer SBI Barnch Gadge Nagar Amravati ,elaborated talk on Competitive examination base on undergraduate study, & Inspired the students in many ways on dated 07 Jan 2016
3. Department of Chemistry organized yearly Seminar session for Chemistry offering undergraduate students in late memory of Dr.N.V.Bhamburkar on dated 15 Jan 2016
Guest: - i) Dr.P.R.Padole Shri Shivaji Science college Amravati. & delivered talk on Periodic Table Chemistry for B.Sc.I students.
ii) Dr.S.V.Kolhe Shivaji College Akot & delivered talk on Carbohydrate Chemistry & inspired students in Many Ways.

Intercollegiate Seminar Competition

- i) Ms.Nikita V. Arbat Ph.Sc.III delivered talk on Mass Spectrometry in Seminar Competition organized at Dr.R.G.Rathod Science College Murtizapur. And Bagged Second Prize in it on dated 27 Feb 2016.
- ii) Ms.Fainaz H.Akbar Ph.Sc.II delivered talk on Metallurgy in Seminar Competition organized at G.S.College Khairgaon & Bagged Consolation Prize on dated 20 feb 2016.

Group Discussion

Department of Chemistry started group discussion in chemistry for B.Sc.III students Many students Participated in discussion and motivated in many ways.

Celebration of Science Day programmes every year .in this year on Feb. 28 & department of Chemistry arranged seminar competition on the occasion of science day.

Departmental Library

Sr.No.	Number of Books	Number of Journals	Number of E-Books
1	38	7	100
Total			145

Head

J.D. PATIL SANGALUDKAR MAHAVIDYALAYA, DARYAPUR
DEPARTMENT OF BOTANY
Departmental Books
SESSION : 2014 – 15

No.of text books in departmental library	No.of journals in departmental library	Study materials in departmental library	Reference books in departmental library
04	04	03	02

PJKarte
(Dr. P. S. Raste)

Department of Music

(2015-16)

Title of Practice:-

Development of the Departmental library by the students donating books

Name of the Department : Indian Music

Information of text books, Journals, Study material and reference books in departmental library till 30 June 2016

No. of Reference Books in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	Study Material in departmental Library
10	10	i) CD's of Raagas prescribed in syllabus of UG & PG.

No. of students donating books - B.A. III Year Students

List of Donated Books :- Kramik Pustak Malika 3 Parts

Department of Music

(2014-15)

Title of Practice:-

Development of the Departmental library by the students donating books

Name of the Department : Indian Music

Information of text books, Journals, Study material and reference books in departmental library till 30 June 2015

No. of Text Books in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	Study Material in departmental Library	Reference Books in Departmental Library
10	02	i) CD's of Raagas prscribed in syllabus of UG & PG. ii)Xerox Copies of Notes UG & PG	Abhinav Geetangali -05 Parts

No. of students donating books - 02 i) Ku. Reshma Karne (M.A.-ii)

ii)Ku. Girija Ganorkar (M.A.-ii)

List of Donated Books

i)Naad Kamal

ii)Bandishincha Bandishi

Department of Music

(2014-15)

Title of Practice:-

Development of the Departmental library by the students donating books

Name of the Department : Indian Music

Information of text books, Journals, Study material and reference books in departmental library till 30 June 2015

No. of Reference Books in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	Study Material in departmental Library
07	05	i) CD's of Raagas prescribed in syllabus of UG & PG.

No. of students donating books - 02 i) Ku. Reshma Karne (M.A.-ii)
ii) Ku. Girija Ganorkar (M.A.-ii)

List of Donated Books

i) Naad Kamal

ii) Bandishincha Bandishi

मराठी विभाग

विभागीय वाचनालय अहवाल

सत्र २०१४-२०१५ या दरम्यान विभागीय वाचनालय निर्माण करण्यात आले. विद्यार्थ्यांना केलेल्या आवाहनानुसार ११ पुस्तके यात जमा केल्या गेले. विद्यार्थ्यांच्या सहकार्याने निर्माण केलेल्या या वाचनालयाचा वापर विद्यार्थी करतात.

उद्देश — या वाचनालय स्थापनेचे उद्देश पुढील प्रकारे आहेत.

१. विद्यार्थ्यांना पुस्तके उपलब्ध व्हावे.
२. विद्यार्थ्यांमध्ये वाचनाची आवड निर्माण करणे.

वाचनालय संदर्भ — शैक्षणिक तसेच संदर्भ ग्रंथांचा संग्रह करून विद्यार्थ्यांना सुलभ पद्धतीने पुस्तके उपलब्ध करून देण्याच्या हेतूने या वाचनालयाची स्थापना करण्यात आली आहे.

वाचनालय पद्धत — विद्यार्थ्यांना पुस्तके देताना त्याची नोंद केल्या जाते. त्याचप्रमाणे त्यांना आवश्यक असलेल्या पुस्तकांची यादा तयार करण्यात येते जेणेकरून आवश्यक पुस्तके उपलब्ध करता येईल.

वाचनालयातील ग्रंथ — या वाचनालयात अकरा पुस्तके आहेत त्याची माहिती खालीलप्रमाणे.

१. जावे त्यांच्या देशा
२. विशाखा काव्यसंग्रह
३. धग
४. मधुकर केचे यांचे साहित्य
५. दृष्टांत पाठ
६. ग्रामगीता
७. तुकाराम गाथा
८. संतसाहित्य
९. बहिणाबाईची कविता
१०. संकल्प भाग १
११. संदेश भाग १

Marathi Department

Departmental library 2015-16

No. of Text book – 04

No. of journal – 05

Study material in Departmental library – Nil

Reference books – 21

No. of Books and Reference books donated by faculties - 30

मराठी विभाग वाचनालय

त्र २०१५ २०१६ दरम्यान खालील पुस्तके मराठी विभाग वाचनालयात समाविष्ट करण्यात आली आहेत.

१. संक्षिप्त आत्मकथा महात्मा गांधी
२. दलित आत्मकथने एक चिंतन - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
३. आसपास ललित लेख संग्रह - डॉ. मिलिंद भिलपवार
४. जागतिकीकरण आणि दलित कविता - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
५. साहित्य दर्शन - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
६. मानवी हक्काबाबत डॉ. आंबेडकरांचे विचार संपादित - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
७. संत व महापुरुष दर्शन संपादित - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
८. दलित स्त्रियांचे आत्मकथने एक मूल्यशोध - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
९. भावमालामासिक
१०. अक्षरवैदर्भी मासिक
११. आधार मासिक
१२. अक्षरगाथा मासिक
१३. सर्वधारा मासिक
१४. महात्मा फुले यांची स्त्रीमुक्ती चळवळ - डॉ. कुसुमेंद्र सोनटक्के
१५. जनसाहित्य - डॉ. सुभाष सावरकर
१६. दलित कवितेतील जननिष्ठ जाणीव - डॉ. नाळकंठ मेंढे
१७. संत एकनाथ व संत तुकाराम
१८. भगवत गीता जशी आहे तशी
१९. आजची मराठी कविता - प्रा. वसंत बापट

मराठी विभाग वाचनालय

सत्र २०१५ २०१६ दरम्यान खालील पुस्तके मराठी विभाग वाचनालयात समाविष्ट करण्यात आली आहेत.

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२. दलित आत्मकथने एक चिंतन - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
३. आसपास ललित लेख संग्रह - डॉ. मिलिंद भिलपवार
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५. साहित्य दर्शन - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
६. मानवी हक्काबाबत डॉ. आंबेडकरांचे विचार संपादित - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
७. संत व महापुरुष दर्शन संपादित - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
८. दलित स्त्रियांचे आत्मकथने एक मूल्यशोध - डॉ. विनोद कोकणे
९. भावमालामासिक
१०. अक्षरवैदर्भी मासिक
११. आधार मासिक
१२. अक्षरगाथा मासिक
१३. सर्वधारा मासिक
१४. महात्मा फुले यांची स्त्रीमुक्ती चळवळ - डॉ. कुसुमेंद्र सोनटक्के
१५. जनसाहित्य - डॉ. सुभाष सावरकर
१६. दलित कवितेतील जननिष्ठ जाणीव - डॉ. नाळकंठ मेंढे
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१८. भगवत गीता जशी आहे तशी
१९. आजची मराठी कविता - प्रा. वसंत बापट

**Shri, Shivaji Education Society Amravati,
J.D.Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur**

Department of Zoology

Departmental Library

Session 2014-15

Sr No	Name of Test Books of Departmental	No. of Journals in Departmental library	Natural shady Material in Departmental library	Name of Reference book in Departmental library
1.	04	03	Nil	02

Head

(.Dr.R.B.Deshmukh)

Department of Zoology

DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY

Departmental Library

Report

2015-16

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List of donated books- Nil
6. Problems encountered and resources required
 1. Lack of accommodation and furniture
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 3. Lack of audio visual aids.

Shri, Shivaji Education Society Amravati,
J.D.Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur
Department of Zoology
Departmental Library
Session 2015-16

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Head

(.Dr.R.B.Deshmukh)

Department of Zoology

DEPARTMENT OF ZOOLOGY

Departmental Library

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Shri Shvaji Education Society Amravati's
J. D. PATIL SANGLUDKAR MAHAVIDYALAYA, DARYAPUR
DIST- AMRAVATI.

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS

DEPARTMENTAL LIBRARY

Session:- 2014-2015

No. of Textbooks in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	Nature of Study Material in Departmental Library	Nature of Reference Books in Departmental Library
04	02	--	--

M.A. Male-de
Head

Shri Shvaji Education Society Amravati's

J. D. PATIL SANGLUDKAR MAHAVIDYALAYA, DARYAPUR

DIST- AMRAVATI.

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS

DEPARTMENTAL LIBRARY

Session:- 2015-2016

No. of Textbooks in Departmental Library	No. of Journals in Departmental Library	Nature of Study Material in Departmental Library	Nature of Reference Books in Departmental Library
04	02	--	--

M.A. Maleode
Head

PRESENTATION OF BEST PRACTICES

BEST PRACTICE- I (Mathematics)

1. **Title:** - Development of departmental Library by the students donating books.
2. **Goals :- i)** To provide books to the students for preparation of various competitive exams in Mathematics.
ii) To enrich the departmental sectional library so as to improve study material.
3. **The Context:** - To increase the awareness of the students with respect to mathematics by reading books.
4. **The practise:** - We arrange the group discussion of B.Sc.-III students based on the library books.

5. Evidence Of Success:-

Number of students donating books:- 02

List of Donated Books:-

- a) Modern Algebra by T. M. Karade,
- b) Partial Differential Equation by T. M. Karade.

6. Problem encounter & Resources required: - Nil

7/8/2015
M. A. M. de
(Mathematics)

J. D. Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur

Department of English

Departmental Library

Title of the practice- Development of departmental library through the contribution of students and teachers

Goals-

- To inculcate reading habits among the students.
- To enrich their language by exposing them to good literature
- To provide them examples of good writing in English for improving their writing skills
- To develop moral values among the students

The Context-

As the most of the students come from the poor and disadvantaged section of society, they are not capable of purchasing even their textbooks. The copies of textbooks available in the central library are not adequate. As such the students can be benefited by the departmental library that will provide them not only text books but also reference books and other books of literature. This practice of donating books to the departmental library will also inculcate the spirit of co-operation and comprehensive outlook of the students.

Practice-

The students donate their previous year books to the departmental library. These books are issued to the students who cannot afford to buy them. The teachers also donate books to the departmental library in order to inculcate reading habits among the students. These books mainly include story books, novels and great classics.

Evidence of success-

- No of books donated by students - 3
- No. of books donated by teachers - 4

List of the books donated by students

- 1) Fast Track I
- 2) Fast Track II
- 3) Bliss of Solitude

List of the books donated by teachers-

- 1) Black Beauty - Anna Sewell
- 2) Hayavadana - Girish Karnad
- 3) A Background to the Study of English Literature
- 4) A Background to the Study of English Literature

Problems encountered and Resources required

Problems encountered-

- The number of students donating books is very less as compared to the number of students demanding them.
- Lack of special financial provisions/funds for the purpose
- Lack of adequate infrastructure.

Resources required-

- Separate reading room is required.

Dr. N. T. Mane
HEAD
Department of English
Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya
-ARYAPUR, Dist. Amravati.